

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Solutions for the final sorting of Bulky Waste

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the current bulky waste streams and technologies utilized for the wooden, fibre and plastic fraction of the municipal bulky waste and their potential integration in the circular material supply chain of ECOBULK. In order to evaluate the streams, five sorting tests were made with material from German bulky waste collection stations. Advanced sensor-based sorting solutions such as NIR and x-ray technologies were used to recover recyclables from the bulky waste streams which are currently often incinerated or landfilled. Major technical challenges are the heterogeneous and varying composition and the handling due to size and geometry of the bulky waste. The optimal balance of achievable recovery rates and high purities without compromising the technical and economic feasibility of the final products is addressed.

For the five bulky waste streams pretreatment steps were necessary. The pretreatment consisted of crushing, screening, ballistic separation and metal separation. They were adjusted depending on the different bulky waste stream composition.

The main recovered materials were wood, rigid plastics, flexible plastics, refuse-derived fuel, metals and fibers. Additionally, wood waste coming from bulky waste was cleaned to produce wood chips. These wood chips were used for the chipboard industry and shall give an example of the circular material supply chain. Furthermore, plastic fractions from municipal solid waste were recovered and sent to ECOBULK partners for further processing.

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1. Introduction

Bulky waste is a very heterogeneous material flow consisting of big pieces which are very difficult to handle. The transport is complicated and the break down is expensive. Most of the time, the material which is coming from bulky waste is incinerated or landfilled. The amount which is disposed in Europe is about 50 million tons every year (Green, E., & Award, C., 2013). Therefore, the reduction of the incineration of valuable material such as fibers, wood and plastics is essential to achieve the European targets of recycling rates and future goals of landfill bans.

Advanced solutions for sorting of current heterogeneous waste streams need to be evaluated to include the potential of the recovered materials in the circular material supply chain. Crushing techniques, automated sorting and treatment technologies are involved in the process of finding the optimal way of implementing products which are designed for the linear supply chain in the circular material supply chain of ECOBULK.

1.1. Description of the document and pursue

The document evaluates the current waste stream of bulky waste. Furthermore, it establishes the optimal use of existing sorting technologies. The technologies applied include FLYING BEAM®, AUTOSORT, X-TRACT and AUTOSORT FLAKE from TOMRA.

The aim is to evaluate the streams in order to reenter the materials coming from linear designed products in the circular material supply chain of ECOBULK.

Therefore, bulky waste streams are described and, based on examples, their composition is evaluated. The material is coming from German bulky waste collection stations. It is sorted in different fractions to get a product which is useable for further processing. The sorted products are wood, rigid plastics, flexible plastics, refuse-derived fuel and fibers. In addition, a cleaning step with a woodchip fraction was realized. The woodchip fraction which comes initially from bulky waste is used for the chipboard production. This example of a closed loop is meant to emphasize the possibilities to integrate recovered material in the circular material supply chain of ECOBULK.

Additionally, the scheme of existing bulky waste treatment plants is explained as well as the applied sorting technologies.

Furthermore, plastic fractions from municipal solid waste were recovered to use them in further processing steps of ECOBULK partners. Therefore, the process to achieve a recycled plastic product with a quality similar to virgin products is explained.

1.2. WPs, Tasks and deviations related with the deliverable

This deliverable refers to Work Package 5, Task 5.3 Current bulky and ELV waste streams: Revalorization for integration in circular material supply chain.

The predefined action plan for Sub task 5.3.1 was as follow:

1. to ship from project partner shredded materials to the German test centre and assess the material input mass balance,
2. agree on which materials need to be recovered with the material development partners and (re-) manufacturers,
3. recover these materials and measure outputs,
4. agree on a required material purity for material further processing,
5. and then repeat steps for different materials.

Due to changes in the Consortium at the beginning of the Ecobulk project (ARN was replaced by BELLVER PLA GROUP and AIMPLAS), as well as no demand on material samples from Ecobulk partners, the new action plan had to be defined and it was as follow:

1. organize already shredded bulky waste material and assess the material input mass balance.
2. define which materials should be sorted,
3. recover these materials and measure outputs,
4. ship sorted wood fractions from bulky waste to project partners (IPCP CNR and Tecnotex) for further testing,
5. ship treated PP pellets from household waste to project partner (Coventive Composites) for further testing.

Point 4 was done with different material than point 1. Because there was no demand from project partners of sorted fractions after testing, the results were recorded, and the material

was disposed. Delayed material requests were provided with material from other customers tests done with bulky waste samples. Those samples coming from an English bulky waste plant, was chosen because of similar properties as the tested material from point 1.

The sent material samples mentioned in Point 4 provided input for task 3.1. Material samples from point 5 were sent for characterization as part of Task 5.3.3. Further processing steps will be carried out by the project partners.

2. Bulky Waste

Bulky waste is described as waste material which is too large to be accepted by the regular waste collection. In many countries it is either picked up from streets or pavements of the area or recycling stations are installed in some areas where the residents can bring their waste. Depending on the locally waste management this service is provided free of charge or a fee has to be paid. Examples of bulky waste items include discarded furniture like couches, chairs or tables, white goods like refrigerators, electronic waste like ovens or TVs, and plumbing fixtures like bathtubs or toilets.

The most interesting material fractions in terms of amount and recyclability are wood, fibers, metals and plastic fractions. Additionally, the residue material is often cleaned from polyvinyl chloride (PVC) to make it usable as refuse-derived fuel (RDF). RDF can be used for example together with traditional sources of fuel in coal power plants or in the cement kiln industry.

2.1. Process Scheme of Bulky Waste Plant

Figure 1 shows a typical scheme of a bulky waste treatment plant. Depending on the input material, the equipment used and produced products can vary from plant to plant. In this simplified scheme the products are metals, wood, fibers, flexible plastics and rigid plastics. The equipment used are:

- Screen for size separation
- Magnet for metal separation
- Eddy Current for non-ferrous metal separation
- Ballistic separator for divide the stream in 2D material and 3D material fractions
- Manual sorting in sorting cabins
- Sensor based sorting with different settings depending on the desired material

Normally, in the delivery of the bulky waste an acceptance control is performed. Special attention is given to the presence of hazardous substances. By sending the products to an additional sensor-based sorting step, specific qualities of materials or types of materials can be produced. For example, the plastic fraction can be sorted additionally in polypropylene (PP),

polyethylene (PE) and polystyrene (PS). Depending on the input material and market conditions additional sorting steps make economically sense or not. For the quality control, either sensor-based sorting or manual sorting is used.

The residue material needs to be incinerated or landfilled.

Figure 1: Scheme for bulky waste treatment

2.2. Process Technology

Advanced automated sensor-based sorting systems use, as working principle, some physical-chemical properties of the different materials such as density, electrical conductivity or magnetic susceptibility, as well as surface and material properties, such as the infrared spectrum or the colour.

Near-infrared (NIR) spectrometers, colour (VIS) sensors and cameras, electromagnetic (EM) sensors and to lower extent X-ray systems have found the widest distribution within the waste and recycling industry. A single machine can also use a combination of multiple sensors.

Within this project the sorting of bulky waste fractions in grain sizes from 400 mm down to 6 mm was performed by using high resolution sorting units.

Within WP5 different advanced sorting technologies, as

- NIR/VIS sensors
- X-ray sensors and
- EM sensors

were applied and adapted in sorting tests on collected bulky waste. Based on current developments, Tomra adapted their technology to the specific problem of the bulky waste recycling. The functional principles of the automated sorting technologies are described in the following sections.

2.2.1. Near Infrared Technology

The Autosort provides a high degree of flexibility. This product is using the DUOLINE® scanning technology which conducts a double scan on every pass. Extremely fast near infrared (NIR) and visible light (VIS) spectrometer based sensors take in the characteristic spectra with a very high optical resolution. The double scanning process makes it possible to significantly increase the distance between the scanner unit and the conveyor belt while maintaining the high resolution. This minimizes the soiling of the optical components and significantly increases the reliability.

The advanced NIR spectrometer based detector recognizes materials based on their specific and unique spectral properties of reflected light. There are two detectors available for different spectral ranges.

The VIS spectrometer based detector recognises materials based on their specific colour properties.

These detectors can be used in combination depending on the application.

The system can be quickly optimized for the required sorting tasks by the selection of sorting programs.

Figure 2: principle of the Tomra Autosort

Input material (1) is evenly fed onto a conveyor belt, where it is detected by the NIR and/or VIS spectrometer based detector (2). If the sensors detect material to be sorted out, it commands the control unit to blow the appropriate valves of the ejection module at the end of the conveyor belt. The detected materials are separated from the material flow by jets of compressed air. The sorted material is divided into two or three fractions in the separation chamber (3).

In Figure 3 the Tomra Autosort machine is shown. The orange scanner box sends a strip of near-infrared light on the conveyor belt.

In Figure 4 the Autosort Flake is shown. This machine among others was used to produce the plastics material out of household waste. The sensor technique used is as well the NIR/VIS

technology. The mechanical set up is optimized for very small particle sizes like plastic flakes. The smallest sortable particle size for the Autosort Flake is about two Millimeters (mm).

Figure 4: Tomra Autosort

Figure 3: Autosort Flake, principle and image

2.2.2. X-ray Technology

The Tomra X-tract (shown in Figure 5) uses an electric x-ray source and a highly sensitive x-ray camera with DUOLINE® sensor technology. This is using two independent sensor lines with different spectral sensitivities. The data supplied by this camera is classified using Tomra high speed x-ray processing. So the atomic density of the materials can be identified and this is largely accomplished regardless of the material thickness.

The machine can be quickly optimized for the required sorting tasks by the selection of sorting programs and sensitivity adjustments.

The Tomra X-tract separator is independent of surface quality of the material to be sorted. Colour and contaminations by dirt, dust, paint, etc. are irrelevant to the detection. The X-rays treat the material by passing through, which actually gives information on the complete material piece and not only of the surface. The principle is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Image of X-tract machine

Figure 6: Principle of X-tract

Input material (1) is evenly fed over a vibration feeder onto a high speed conveyor belt. An electric X-ray source (3) generates a broad-band radiation. This radiation penetrates the material and the transmitted x-rays are received by the x-ray camera (2) with DUOLINE® sensor. If the sensor detects material to be sorted out, commands the control unit to blow the appropriate valves of the ejection module at the end of the conveyor belt.

2.3. Test Procedure

2.3.1. TOMRA Test Facility

The testing of the bulky waste samples took place at the Tomra test facility in Mülheim Kärlich in Germany.

Tomra's test facility for automatic sorting is the only one of its kind worldwide. Set out in a loop which initially prepares the waste by screening combined with the use of a ballistic separator, the test facility features all of associated sorting and recycling technologies, like near-infrared (NIR) and visual (VIS) spectroscopy, electromagnetic sensors, x-ray-sensors, colour cameras etc.

The test facility was designed to allow several different processes to run concurrently which can accurately simulate a customer's facility and operating environment. The loop is shown in Figure 7.

Changes can be made during the testing phase which ensures that Tomra sorting systems are calibrated to deliver optimum levels of sorting and recycling for each individual customer's requirements.

Figure 7: Loop of test center

2.3.2. Pretreatment of the bulky waste

To enhance the sortability of the very heterogeneous input material a pretreatment is necessary. Firstly, a shredding step is conducted to comminute the oversized pieces, followed by a screening step to reassure that oversized pieces are not going through the process line. Another screening step is conducted to get the fine material out. Next, a ballistic separator sorts the material in a 2D and 3D fraction. The 2D fraction which contains the flat materials include for example film and fiber while the 3D fraction which contains rolling material include for example wood and rigid plastic. Then, these two fractions are going to the optical sorting units. Either in the end of the 3D fractions or on the beginning, a metal separator and/or an eddy current separator can be added to sort out metals and non-ferrous metals.

The different pretreatment steps are depending on the composition of the input material.

In the following chapter 2.4 the pretreatment steps for each test carried out in the Tomra test center are shown.

2.4. Test Results

Test materials were derived from bulky waste from municipal collection and also from commercial and industrial waste sources (C&I). Some of the input materials tested contain fractions from both sources, as the waste management companies that treat the material often receive waste from both streams.

The weights are shown in kilograms (kg) and the throughput in tons per hour per meter of bandwidth (t/h/m).

After a visual assessment of the material stream it was decided which fractions should be recovered.

2.4.1. Test 1

Material description	Bulky waste
Country of origin	Germany
Particle size distribution	<60 mm, 60-150mm and >150mm
Pre-treatment before testing	- screening - metal separation
Products generated	- wood

Figure 8: PVC (coating is PVC)

Figure 9: Wood/Residues

Bulky waste - Medium	kg	
Total	84,70	100,0%

Throughput
5,08 t/h/m

manually

Non-fer. metals	kg	
Total	1,60	1,9%

step 1
EJECT

Impurities	kg	
Total	3,60	4,3%

ACCEPT

Wood	kg	
Total	79,50	93,9%

Figure 10: Impurities

Figure 11: Wood and non-ferrous metals

Bulky waste - Coarse	kg	
Total	148,30	100,0%

Figure 12: Non-ferrous metals

Figure 13: Impurities step 1

Figure 14: Wood

Figure 15: Impurities step 2

At test 1 three different grain size fractions were generated by screening. Figure 8 and Figure 9 are showing the product after sorting of the fines fraction, Figure 10 and Figure 11 are showing the product after sorting of the medium fraction and Figure 12, Figure 13, Figure 14 and **Error! Reference source not found.** are showing the generated material fractions of the coarse fraction.

2.4.2. Test 2

Material description	Mix of bulky waste and C&I
Country of origin	Germany
Particle size distribution	80-150 mm
Pre-treatment before testing	- screening - ballistic separation
Products generated	- with 2D-material: PE film, paper, refuse-derived fuel - with 3D-material: rigid plastics, wood, refuse-derived fuel

Figure 16: Input material of test 2

Ballistic Separation:

Figure 17: 3D Material

Figure 18: 2D material

2D Material:

Figure 19: PE film

Figure 20: Paper

Figure 21: PVC

Figure 22: Refuse-derived fuel

3D Material:

Figure 23: Plastics

Figure 24: Wood

Figure 25: Refuse-derived fuel

Figure 26: Residue

At test 2 the input material (shown in Figure 16) is sorted with a ballistic separator in a 2-dimensional (2D) fraction shown in Figure 18 and 3-dimensional (3D) fraction shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** With each fraction a sensor-based sorting step was carried out. The generated products of the 2D fraction are shown in Figure 19, Figure 20, Figure 21 and Figure 22. The generated products of the 3D fractions are shown in Figure 23, Figure 24, Figure 25 and Figure 26.

2.4.3. Test 3

Material description	Mix of bulky waste and C&I
Country of origin	Germany
Particle size distribution	35-300 mm
Pre-treatment before testing	- screening - ballistic separation
Products generated	- with 2D-material: paper - with 3D-material: wood

Ballistic Separation & Screen:

3D Material >35mm:

Figure 27: Wood

Figure 28: Residue

2D Material:

2D-fraction	kg	
Total	123,6	100,0%
Ref. to input		26,4%

Throughput
0,3t/h/m

step 1
EJECT

Paper	kg	
Total	66,0	53,4%
Ref. to input		14,1%

ACCEPT

Residue	kg	
Total	57,6	46,6%
Ref. to input		12,3%

Figure 29: Paper

Figure 30: Residue

At test 3 a pretreatment of screening and ballistic separation was carried out. Two fractions (2D and 3D>35mm) were sorted by sensor-based sorting. The generated material of the 3D>35mm fraction and 2D fraction are shown in Figure 27, Figure 28, Figure 29 and Figure 30.

2.4.4. Test 4

Material description	Mix of bulky waste and C&I
Country of origin	Germany
Particle size distribution	80-150 mm
Pre-treatment before testing	- screening - ballistic separation
Products generated	- with 2D-material: PE film, paper, refuse-derived fuel - with 3D-material: rigid plastics, wood, refuse-derived fuel

Ballistic Separation:

2D Material:

Figure 31: PE-film

Figure 32: Paper, cardboard

Figure 33: PVC

Figure 34: Refuse-derived fuel

3D Material:

Figure 35: Plastics

Figure 36: Wood

Figure 37: Refuse-derived fuel

Figure 38: Residue

At test 4 a 2D and 3D fraction with ballistic separation was generated. The 2D material was sorted in four different fractions shown in Figure 31, Figure 32, Figure 33 and Figure 34. The materials sorted from the 3D fractions are shown in Figure 35, Figure 36, Figure 37 and Figure 38.

2.4.5. Test 5

Material description	Wood waste
Country of origin	Germany
Particle size distribution	10-50 mm
Pre-treatment before testing	- screening
Products generated	- Wood chips

Wood waste:

Total	kg	
Total	255.90	100.00%
Composition Input		
Impurities	0.61	0.80%
Wood	75.00	99.20%
	75.61	100.00%

Throughput
18.42 t/h/m

STEP 1
EJECT

REJECT

Impurities	kg	
Total	1.10	0.43%
Composition Eject		
Impurities	0.60	55.56%
Wood	0.48	44.44%
	1.08	100.00%

Wood	kg	
Total	254.80	99.57%
Composition Reject		
Impurities	0.008	0.01%
Wood	75.00	99.99%
	75.01	

Figure 39: Wood chip product

Figure 40: Residue

At test 5 a wood waste fraction was sorted. The wood fraction coming from bulky waste was sorted to produce a wood chip fraction (shown in Figure 39) for the chipboard industry. The residue fraction is shown in Figure 40.

3. Plastics Material

Due to a request of another Ecobulk project partner, also plastics material from municipal solid waste was provided. Using the Autosort and the Autosort Flake in different processing steps, various plastic fractions were sorted by type and color. The provided material was a clear PP fraction in form of pellets. The whole process chain for recovering the PP pellets is seen in Figure 41.

Figure 41: Process chain for recovering plastics material out of household waste

4. Summary and Conclusion

The potential of the integration in the circular material supply chain of ECOBULK was shown by sorting out the valuable materials of German bulky waste streams.

The compositions of the five tests are shown in Table 1. The main recovered materials were wood, rigid plastics, flexible plastics, refuse-derived fuel, metals and fibers. The biggest fraction at test 1 is the wood fraction with 47.7%. The material of test 2 consisted mostly of refuse-derived fuel which is used to produce electricity in waste-to-energy plants and is therefore classified as thermal recycling material. Referring to material recycling, the biggest fraction is PE-film with 13.0%. At test 3 a high amount of wood was recovered. The material of test 4 consisted of several different recyclables. The biggest part after the RDF material is a paper/cardboard fraction. Additionally, wood waste coming from bulky waste was cleaned to produce wood chips (test 5). These wood chips were used for the chipboard industry and shall give an example of the circular material supply chain.

Furthermore, plastic fractions from municipal solid waste were recovered and sent to Coventive Composites where further processing steps are implemented.

Table 1: Composition of bulky waste streams tested

Test 1	PVC 0.2%	Non-ferrous metalls 2.4%	Wood 47.7%	Residue 49.8%			
Test 2	PE-film 13.0%	Paper 11.5%	PVC 3.4%	RDF 43.0%	Plastics 8.8%	Wood 6.7%	Residues 13.5%
Test 3	Wood 38.8%	Paper 14.1%	Residue 47.1%				
Test 4	PE-film 9.0%	Paper/cardboard 17.2%	PVC 6.4%	RDF 38.8%	Plastics 4.2%	Wood 2.7%	Residues 21.7%
Test 5	Wood chips 99.6%	Residue 0.4%					

It has been shown that with the NIR and x-ray sensor-based technologies the targeted materials were successfully separated. Special attention has to be dedicated to the pretreatment steps because it has been shown to be a key aspect for a proper separation process. For all five bulky waste streams pretreatment steps were necessary. The pretreatment consisted of crushing,

screening, ballistic separation and metal separation. They were adjusted depending on the different bulky waste stream composition.

Further investigation in subsequent treatment possibilities should be conducted to evaluate the quality of the recovered material and find suitable end applications to close the material supply chain. This work is already ongoing in WP3.